

THE HABITAT FOUNDATION

THE BIODIVERSITY OF THE BALKANS IN GBIF

FINAL REPORT

SEPTEMBER 2025

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SUMMARY

The project set out to support the mobilisation of biodiversity data from the Balkans, with an initial goal to publish between 144,000 and 250,000 records from this region. The project plan included engaging specialists across various taxa from five countries and offering practical training sessions on preparing and publishing biodiversity data. This approach aimed to promote data collection, digitisation, standardisation, and publication practices.

The project aimed to publish at least 175,000 records by its conclusion, achieving a 10% increase in the available biodiversity data from the Balkans.

By the project's final reporting, 1,441,356 records on the Balkan's biodiversity had been published, which presents an increase of 89% in the biodiversity data in the GBIF. It includes occurrence data on mammals and birds from Bulgaria, former Yugoslavia, Montenegro and Albania.

Specialists from Bulgaria, Serbia, Romania, North Macedonia, Kosovo, Montenegro, and Albania were informed, trained at various levels, and actively involved in data publishing.

The Balkans, known for their rich biodiversity and diverse habitats, remain understudied, putting species of conservation concern in the region at risk.

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Belma Šestović (Wildlife Montenegro) dissects a Blind mole (Spalax spp) to collect DNA material to verify the species.

PROJECT GROUP

1. Svetlana Miteva – project coordinator
2. Dimitri Brosens – project advisor

APPLICANT

Established in 2010, **The Habitat Foundation (THF)** of The Netherlands is dedicated to fostering knowledge exchange, facilitating targeted cooperation, and supporting organisations and individuals engaged in nature research, management and conservation.

Operating primarily in South-Eastern and Eastern Europe, THF collaborates closely with non-governmental organisations and governmental organisations.

This project is in line with THF's mission, focusing on capacity building, optimising biodiversity information, and promoting international cooperation to advance evidence-based nature conservation efforts in Europe.

PROJECT PARTNERS

National Museum of Natural History Sofia, Bulgaria

Nedko Nedyalkov – mammals
Nia Toshkova – bats

Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds, Bulgaria

Georgi Popgeorgiev – data manager of the Smart Birds data platform and mobile application of the Bulgarian Society for the Protection of Birds (BSPB)

Wildlife Montenegro, Montenegro

Belma Sestovich / Marina Radonjić – mammals

Protection and Preservation of Natural Environment in Albania (PPNEA), Albania

Bledi Hoxha, Aleksandër Trajçe, Melitijan Nezaj – mammals and birds

Fund for Wild Flora and Fauna – Bulgaria

Hristo Peshev – vultures researcher and data manager

MOTIVATION

WHY mobilise biodiversity data from the Balkans?

The Balkans are identified as a European biodiversity hot spot and part of the Mediterranean Key Biodiversity Area (KBA). The Balkans include parts of Croatia, the whole of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Greece, Serbia, Bulgaria and the European part of Turkey.

Reliable up-to-date data on species occurrence allows evidence-based conservation and nature management, as well as the development of further studies on the biodiversity of the Balkans. Unfortunately, the geographically referenced species occurrence data from the Balkans is scarce. Baseline data on many groups like mammals, insects, plants, reptiles and amphibians is absent.

PRODUCTS

The main project's product was as planned: to publish as many biodiversity records as possible (at least 400,000 records, as mentioned in the amended project in November 2023) and also to mainstream and build capacity in data mobilisation and data publication in the Balkans.

PROJECT ACHIEVEMENTS

The project has assisted the publication of 1,441,356 records on biodiversity and works towards the publication of more data. The data sets published so far are presented in the table below.

N of records	Links to the data sets published within this project
221,699 Birds Bulgaria	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0c5f7cb7-1973-4f0e-994f-dfc69fcabc0e
131,502 Birds Bulgaria	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7683cc47-cb13-4bad-9614-387c66aa8df0
87,747 Birds Bulgaria	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7cb27130-4d5e-44f6-9dc1-7939bc90fdf6
1,246 Birds Albania	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a3fa8e8d-455d-46bc-a8f1-05914ce9c46a
973,808 Griffon Vulture movement data	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/882161ab-5a7a-4206-b757-3f3383f4f363
3,796 data Mammal Field Study Group	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/41cb0352-7afd-467f-8d1f-49bf69919463
4,021 Mammals Bulgaria	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/5fd5f65d-e903-4a23-83e1-f34e15e17c93
5,638 Mammals Yugoslavia (1992)	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/9d44512b-1bc3-47e9-b186-73b2aff9f38e
1,696 Mammals Montenegro	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d8a37dba-3d99-4634-ab4f-7b8d010c1a6a
10,203 Mammals (bats) Bulgaria	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/6b2a3042-db4f-4bf2-85a4-0301654a083a#contacts

The total number of records on biodiversity available in GBIF from Albania, Bulgaria, Montenegro and Serbia, part of former Yugoslavia, at the start of the project was about 1,621,586.

The 1,441,356 records published by this project present an increase of 89% in the published data on biodiversity from the Balkans.

The project continues to face a primary challenge: a general reluctance and apprehension towards data publication among potential contributors. Additionally, preparing datasets for GBIF publication requires specialised expertise and a certain level of "GBIF fluency". To address this, The Habitat Foundation provided (and still does) personal (online and hands-on) assistance to partners, guiding them in preparing datasets and metadata or simply performing parts of the work to prepare the dataset for publication. This support is generously offered by Dimitri Brosens, a board member of The Habitat Foundation and a GBIF expert.

One of the issues encountered was a publisher's refusal to accept a manuscript for a scientific publication because the data had already been published or was available on the internet in the Smart Birds data platform of BSPB. A publication on 3 species of invasive mammals was refused by Mammalia because the data used in the publication was published in Smart Birds and collected by volunteers, and thus not collected by the authors of the publication.

Initially, the project aimed to publish datasets on mammals, fish, amphibians, reptiles, insects and plants. Unfortunately, some researchers with whom the project had agreements couldn't deliver as planned. After the project began, several researchers faced additional workload pressures or realised their data required extensive work to make it suitable for publication — lacking critical details such as location, coordinates, dates, or existing only in paper form.

In collaboration with the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia, The Habitat Foundation published a valuable dataset with 10,203 records on bats in April 2025. This dataset includes data from many years and various sponsors, data owners, and authors. After lengthy communications with data owners, this data set is finally available in the GBIF database, and we hope it will be a good example of cooperation and a contemporary approach to data sharing and management.

Ultimately, the project successfully published valuable datasets on mammals and birds, and the team is actively working toward publishing additional datasets beyond the project's targets.

BUDGET AND FINANCIAL REPORT

The project received a grant of €30,000. Due to the unexpected prolonging of the work, the project period was extended. However, the project published more data with the available funds than initially envisaged.

Task/person	Details	Days	Fee p/d	Fee x days
Project kick-off meeting				
Provided online training and instructions to the data publishers				-
Data mobilization				
Nedko Nedyalkov NMNH Sofia, BG	mammals, Bulgaria+Balkans	25	60	€ 1.500
Nia Toshkova NMNH Sofia, BG	bats, Bulgaria+Balkans	25	60	€ 1.500
Belma Sestovich & Marina Radonich Wildlife MNE	mammals, Montenegro	18	60	€ 1.080
Bledi Hoxha & Alex Traiche PPNEA, Albania	birds, Albania+Balkans	15	60	€ 900
Georgi Popgeorgiev, BSPB - Smartbirds mob app, BG	birds Bulgaria	200	60	€ 12.000
Hristo Peshev, Fund for Wild Flora and Fauna, BG	vultures Bulgaria	34	60	€ 2.040
Svetlana Miteva, FSG/DMS, NL	mostly mammals Balkans	45	60	€ 2.700
Project overall coordination & reporting				
Svetlana Miteva	Project coordinator THF	52	105	€ 5.460
Operational costs	Website, communication, printed materials			€ 2.720
Subtotaal				€ 29.900
Budget granted				€ 30.000